

IMPAIRMENT OF STUDENTS' ORAL SPEECH IN ENGLISH

Rakhimov M.O.

Senior teacher of Tashkent International University of Financial Management and Technologies

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14017393>

Abstract. *For English language learners, speaking is regarded as one of the primary communication skills. Students tend to experience problems along the process of learning and strengthening speaking skills. The goal of the current research is to investigate the issues that EFL students have in the classroom and the main factors that contribute to these difficulties.*

Keywords: *difficulties, English as a foreign language, speaking ability, psychological aspects, correctness, and efficacy.*

It is not surprise that English language teachers worldwide are concerned about speaking issues, as educators, we know that effective communication is essential to successful learning. Children with strong communication skills are better able to convey their thoughts and feelings, understand and explain the world around them, and form friendships. A child with strong language abilities can think and learn. They also support the growth of one's sense of self and community or group affiliation.

We might ask how to help a student who has speech and language impairments in our class get the most from our lectures. We can significantly impact these students and help them have effective and pleasurable learning experiences if we are aware of many types of speech and language impairments and have some helpful teaching techniques.

What is speech and language impairment?

Individual differences in speech and language impairment can range from minor to severe. Speaking "expressive language" or comprehending "receptive language" can be challenging for a student. They could struggle with social interaction and emotional expression. This may result in low self-esteem, frustration, and behavioral issues in the classroom. Since speech and language issues are not always evident, we must consider the underlying causes of the behavior as well as the needs the learner may be attempting to communicate.

In addition to having additional specific learning disabilities like dyslexia, dyspraxia, or ADHD, the majority of children with speech or language impairments have average intellect. Autism, Down syndrome, cerebral palsy, hearing loss, and other disorders are occasionally associated with speech and language difficulty. Another possible cause is persistent ear infections. Some students require instruction in the communication abilities that other students pick up naturally because they struggle with both language intake and output.

Expressive language difficulties

Some students struggle with the musculoskeletal motions required to create words. They might simply omit some noises because they have problems making them, or they might replace one sound with another. This can lead to delayed or ambiguous communication and making them hard to comprehend.

The capacity to recount stories with the events in the correct order and to put words in sentences might also be impacted by expressive language issues. They may speak incoherently. The student's speech may occasionally sound immature for their age due to the employment of improper grammar structures. Additionally, they could struggle to acquire and access terminology.

Both in their native tongue and when learning English, these issues will surface. It's challenging to participate in class discussions when you struggle to describe and explain topics.

Receptive language difficulties

Some students struggle with language processing and hearing. This may affect one's capacity to comprehend what other people are saying and react correctly. In addition to physical barriers that prevent them from understanding speech, learners with hearing impairments may also experience "pragmatic language" challenges, in which they are able to hear what is being said but are unable to comprehend its meaning. They might not be intuitively aware of social signs and customs, nor do they know how to use social language. Additionally, there may be issues comprehending "figurative language," which encompasses the use of metaphor, irony, and humor.

This can lead to a tendency to take things too literally. A learner with receptive language difficulties may have trouble in one or more of these areas.

Following instructions

Understanding abstract concepts

Concentration

Understanding stories, both written and spoken

Understanding metaphorical language

Making friends

Listening to others

Teaching and learning strategies – how can we help?

Encourage and accept all forms of communication

Students who struggle with speech and language are often anxious and uncomfortable speaking in front of others, so do not urge them to repeat words or full statements. Modeling the proper form in your response is ideal. Pay greater attention to the learner's intended message rather than the grammar. Allow alternative modes of communication, such as writing, painting, or gestures.

2. Be conscious of your own communication style

Make sure your sentences are clear and unambiguous, and face the students so they can see your facial expressions and, if necessary, read your lips. Give directions one at a time, in the order you want them to be followed, and support them with gestures and visual signs. If you shout out the learner's name before asking a question, it will be clear that you want their attention. Avoid ambiguous terms and be prepared to clarify whatever the student does not understand.

3. Teach active listening skills

Emphasize to the pupils the importance of paying attention, looking at the person speaking, and not interrupting. The "speaker's token" is a distinctive item that can be used to teach turn-taking. The only person who can speak is the one holding the object. They pass it on after they're finished.

4. Give time to think and respond to questions

This can be beneficial for all students. The "think, pair, share" technique in the classroom allows pupils to organize their ideas and examine material before answering.

5. Use sound discrimination exercises

We understand that phonemes are the fundamental components of language. Multisensory exercises, such as clapping and stomping on syllables in new vocabulary or color-coding the various phoneme groups, can help kids who struggle with phoneme recognition and decoding.

Card games requiring students to match the same sounds, such as rhyming bingo, can be quite effective.

6. Help with sequencing and word order

If the student is having difficulty presenting concepts or narrating stories, just ask them to supply bullet points of what they want to say and arrange them in the appropriate order on a timeline. Cutting up stories allows children to practice sequencing them; for younger kids, pictures can be used instead.

7. Build vocabulary

Use visuals, objects, and photographs to aid in the learning and recall of new vocabulary. Make a personalized vocabulary box with significant concepts on graphic cards to help children use their visual memory.

8. Help build self-esteem

Make sure you recognize and reward effective communication and relationships. Identify and capitalize on their other attributes, such as physical prowess and originality, in addition to discussing their strengths.

9. Help learners to make their needs known. Check the learner's understanding of the work at all times and address any uncertainty. Encourage them to utilize a predetermined signal to notify you if they have not understood.

English is an international language which is spoken by most people around the world. English is mainly utilized in professional and educational settings for communication. English is taught as a foreign language in Uzbekistan and is now required coursework for students enrolled in elementary, middle, and upper grades. It is required of university students to be able to communicate in spoken English when they practice in the workplace. Nobody disputed that being able to speak the language fluently is necessary for having a discussion. Given that English is an international language, high school students who want to be masters in the workforce should also be fluent in the language [1]. It is imperative that they understand how to strike up a discussion, carry it on, and terminate it with their peers, professors, and clients. Students need to acquire knowledge in three areas: (1) language elements, which include vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation; (2) language functions, which deal with speaking performance in the form of transaction and interaction. (3) The sociocultural norms, which include understanding how to take into account who is speaking to whom, in what conditions, about what, and for what purpose, as well as turn-taking, speech tempo, duration of pauses between speakers, and the relative roles of participants [2]. In keeping with these areas of knowledge, students try to increase their capacity to effectively communicate through speaking. They are not limited to word pronunciation; they also possess the ability to construct coherent sentences using words and expand their vocabulary. In order to interact effectively with others, they would still need to understand the purposes of language and the social and cultural conventions.

Furthermore, it was [2] discussed a few non-linguistic components—such as gestures, body language, intonations, and facial expressions—that help communication be understood. We can sum up by saying that mastering speaking is the most challenging and intricate skill. In order to communicate properly and effectively with the recipient of the message, both linguistic and non-linguistic expertise is required.

Speaking is a productive skill that can be seen directly and experimentally, according to experts [2]. However, the validity and reliability of an oral production test are always compromised

by the efficacy and accuracy of a test-taker's listening skill. This statement claims that speaking abilities of pupils can be evaluated for efficacy and correctness.

Since speaking skill is a productive skill, students have to create their own language to deliver their opinion or when they do communication with others. As a productive skill, speaking skill should be more practiced in order to train students express their ideas. It is not to consume other's language but to produce a language. Relating to produce a language, students should be master in speaking skill. Speaking skills consist of fluency, vocabulary, pronunciation and grammar. It is also supported by gesture, confidence, and motivation. Furthermore, Brown [3] argued that speaking is an interactive process of constructing meaning that involves producing, receiving and processing information. In relation to processing information, students have to understand the spoken language they get. When they are proficient in language, they will process the information with ease. They recognize the words or sounds they hear, at least.

Furthermore, speaking fluently requires not only an understanding of linguistic elements but also the capacity to process both language and information, according to Harmer. The only difficulty an English speaker faces is speaking with fluency. Even when people strive to communicate quickly, poor grammar, improper pronunciation, and improper diction will hinder the message to be understood by the audience. As a result, speakers should be aware of the information that they convey both verbally and nonverbally. Speaking quickly will help their speaking skills perfectly reach the listener.

Speaking fluency is an essential communication ability while interacting with people in the real world. Gaining proficiency in speaking conveys information about the speaker's social status. According to Chomsky [4], an ability is a talent, strength, competency, or knowledge. Speaking ability is the capacity or aptitude to communicate effectively when having a discussion. When the speaker speaks clearly, the listener will grasp what is being said. Speaking clearly entails using appropriate vocabulary, pronouncing words correctly, and adhering to grammar rules. In order to ensure that the discourse is well understood, mimicry, tone, and gestures are also used to support it. Speaking clearly entails using appropriate vocabulary, pronouncing words correctly, and adhering to grammar rules. In order to ensure that the discourse is well understood, mimicry, tone, and gestures are also used to support it. Because of the poor verbal abilities, there is no miscommunication. Additionally, Richard divided the role of speaking in daily life into three categories: speaking as a performance, speaking as a transaction, and speaking as an engagement. It is possible to characterize speaking as people's lives when considering the purpose of speech. They have the ability to communicate, engage in social interactions, transact to meet their wants, and use language to their full potential in society. Contemporary trends encourage more people to talk about a range of issues that affect our society in one way or another. In this context, it is important to recognize that a startlingly high percentage of students struggle on a daily basis when faced with challenging subjects like politics, health, global issues, and too many other things to list. Although at first glance it would seem that this is because of a lack of knowledge, expertise, or a limited viewpoint, a deeper look at the underlying problem shows that there are a number of reasons why students struggle to have productive conversations on difficult subjects. These are a few explanations. Students may find it difficult to participate in conversations on difficult subjects for the following reasons:

1. A shortage of Education and Understanding: Students who don't know enough about the subject matter may find it difficult to grasp complex subjects. It might be challenging to make a

significant contribution to a conversation without a strong information base. Furthermore, the problem is made worse by a lack of knowledge of technical jargon or scientific language pertaining to particular subjects. The issue might have been resolved more readily if behavioral, psychological, social, and mental health issues had not been so common. Addressing the current problem is made more challenging by the prevalence of these worries. Due to a lack of critical thinking skills, a conformist mindset, and a fear of defying social conventions and voicing unconventional opinions, Uzbek youngsters are unable to question established views and Uzbek youth are unable to challenge conventional wisdom and overcome constraining stereotypes and prejudices due to a lack of critical thinking skills, a conformist mindset, and a fear of expressing innovative thoughts.

2. **Lack of Knowledge and Understanding:** Students who are unfamiliar with the subject matter may struggle to grasp complicated concepts. It may be difficult to make a major contribution to a discourse without a solid background knowledge. The problem is aggravated by a lack of understanding of technical jargon or scientific language specific to a certain field. "Differences in mental, social, psychological, and behavioral issues might have made the problem easier to resolve". However, because these concerns are so widespread, it is more difficult.

3. **Fear of Being Judged:** Because they worry about being judged by their teachers or peers, students may be reluctant to participate in conversations on difficult subjects. Their capacity to freely express their ideas and opinions may be hampered by this fear of being criticized.

3. **Lack of Critical Thinking Skills:** In order to analyze data, assess arguments, and formulate well-reasoned judgments, discussing difficult subjects frequently calls for critical thinking abilities. It could be difficult for students who lack these abilities to contribute to conversations in a meaningful manner.

4. **Emotional Reactions:** Students may experience intense emotions when discussing difficult subjects like politics or social issues. Their capacity to have a logical and productive conversation may be hampered by these emotional reactions.

5. **Limited Exposure to Diverse Viewpoints:** Students who have not been exposed to a variety of opinions and viewpoints may find it difficult to understand complex subjects. Students can gain a more sophisticated grasp of complicated subjects by interacting with a variety of viewpoints.

6. **Lack of Confidence:** Students may be reluctant to engage in conversations on difficult subjects, particularly if they are intimidated by their more vocal peers or if they have self-doubt about their capacity to make a significant contribution to the discussion.

7. **Insufficient Support and advice:** If professors or mentors do not provide students with enough support and advice, they may find it difficult to discuss difficult subjects. Students can feel more at ease participating in conversations on difficult topics with the support and encouragement of an effective facilitator.

Speaking challenges are those that cause a person to be less proficient in speaking. According to the Oxford Dictionary (4th edition), difficulties are things that are not simple, require expertise or effort, are troublesome, difficult to do, or difficult to comprehend. Speaking difficulties can be defined as any issues that arise during speech or when attempting to understand spoken language.

In line with the aforementioned description, Doris and Jessica [5] contended that language barriers could be the reason why pupils are unable to enhance their language proficiency. Language

issues are most likely caused by inadequate vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation. These issues fall under the category of linguistic factors. Lack of confidence, nervousness, shyness, fear of making a mistake, and lack of desire are additional issues that can arise when speaking. Those issues are psychological in nature. According to Juhana's research [8], students' ability to speak English in class is hampered by psychological variables like shyness, nervousness, and fear of making a mistake. It indicates that psychological elements as well as a lack of linguistic expertise contribute to students' success in speaking performances.

In their study, Fitriani discovered that psycholinguistic factors accounted for 20.70% of speaking difficulties, with linguistic issues coming in second at 19.59%. For students to be proficient speakers, they must put forth effort. Furthermore, when learning a foreign language, students often struggle with speaking skills like vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation, and fluency. Numerous studies, including those by [8], have demonstrated the challenges that students face when speaking English. They discovered a few issues that lead to students' inability to talk effectively. Speaking difficulties are issues that prevent pupils from speaking. These issues are barriers that prevent pupils from succeeding in speaking English fluently. Speaking is a skill that involves choosing the right words and sentences according on the situation, audience, social setting, and subject matter. As a result, in speaking exercises, one must become proficient in both linguistic and non-linguistic speaking skills.

According to Doris and Jessica [5], one of the main causes of subpar academic achievement is language issues. These issues include psychological issues like low self-esteem, shyness, anxiety, mother tongue language, and lack of motivation to learn, as well as linguistic issues such a lack of vocabulary, grammatical errors, and bad pronunciation. All of these factors contribute to pupils' inability to speak English fluently.

The results of Heriansyah's research [7], which identified five issues and their causes, also support these speaking skill challenges. These issues include: 1) Lack of courage to talk. The reason is a fear of making mistakes and a lack of confidence when speaking. 2) Lack of confidence when speaking, which stems from a fear of making mistakes. 3) The fear of making mistakes was the root cause of the fear of speaking. In conclusion, the pupils themselves reveal the challenges they face.

Students' capacity to communicate is hampered by psychological variables such as shyness, lack of confidence, and fear of making mistakes. These issues can be resolved by starting an English club, encouraging students to talk at all times, giving them more practice with their peers, etc.

It is crucial for teachers to provide a welcoming and inclusive classroom atmosphere that inspires students to freely investigate and debate difficult subjects. Teachers may enable students to participate meaningfully in debates on a variety of significant topics by tackling these concerns and giving them the tools and resources they need.

To sum up, it is important to remember that all of the aforementioned information does help students improve their oral communication skills, and that each of these elements requires repetition, diligence, and perseverance.

REFERENCES

1. Amelia, M. & Komariah E. (2017). Investigating English Speaking Skill Problems Encountered by Students at Islamic Modern Boarding School. READ publication, 119-126

2. Brown, H.D. (2001). Teaching by Principles. An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy. Englewood Cliffs: Prentice Hall.
3. Brown, H.D. (2003). Language Assessment Principle and Classroom Practice. New York. Longman.
4. Chomsky, N. (1965). Persistent Topic in Linguistics Theory. SAGE Journals.
5. Doris & Jessica. (2007). Journal Deaaries Fitria, RW.A Study on the students English Speaking problems in speaking performance.
6. Fulcher. G., Reiter. R. M. (2003). Task Difficulty in Speaking. SAGE Journals. Research articles
7. Heriansyah, H. (2012). Speaking problems faced by the English department students of Syiah Kuala University. *Lingua Didaktika: Journal Bahasa dan Pembelajaran Bahasa*, 6(1), 37-44.
8. Juhana (2012) Psychological Factors That Hinder Students from Speaking in English Class The English Department, Indonesia Open University- *Journal of Education and Practice* www.iiste.org Vol 3, No 12, 2012
9. Kagan. S., Kagan. M. (2009). Teaching to Training Teachers Through Cooperative Learning.
10. Lynch, D., Hennessy, J. (2017). I Choose to Become A Teacher. *Asia- Pacific Journal of Education* 45 (2) p. 106-125
11. Odiljonovich R. M. LEARNING ENGLISH AT SCHOOLS IS CRUCIAL IN TODAY'S GLOBALIZED WORLD FOR SEVERAL REASONS //ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ. – 2023. – Т. 35. – №. 3. – С. 123-125.
12. Ruzmetova D. A., Muratova N. V. ABOUT COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ECONOMIC TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2020. – №. 5. – С. 777-779.